

A Review of Hermite–Hadamard Inequality

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Abstract – In this review we present the most important lines of development, around the well-known Hermite–Hadamard Inequality, as well as some open problems.

Keywords: Hermite–Hadamard inequality; convex function

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most attractive concepts in Mathematical Sciences is the convex function, present today in multiple mathematical areas ranging from Optimization to Function Theory and center of possibly the most fruitful nucleus in the study of inequalities. integral, as we will see later. Let's start by introducing the concept of a convex function as follows.

In what follows, $[a,b]$ is a real, closed and bounded interval. A function $f:[a,b] \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex on the interval $[a,b]$, if the inequality

$$f(tx + (1 - t)y) \leq tf(x) + (1 - t)f(y)$$

holds. We say that f is concave if $-f$ is convex.

We recommend that readers consult the work [21] where a fairly complete overview of the various notions and ramifications is presented. For example, the following graph that illustrates these extensions and derivations of the original concept is interesting.

Fig -1: This figure describes different ramifications derived from the classical definition of convex function, obtained in recent years

With

- {C} Classical convex function.
- {CO} Convexity with respect to another function.
- {SC-C} Strongly convex function with modulus C.
- {HC} Harmonically convex function.
- {SHC-C} Strongly harmonically convex function with modulus C.
- {h-C} h-convex function.
- {P-C} P-convex function.
- {G-L} Godunova–Levin function.
- {S-C} s-convex function.
- {SC-1} s-convex function in the first sense.
- {SC-2} s-convex function in the second sense.
- {m-C} m-convex function.
- {G-C} Geometrically convex function.

- {m-GC} m-geometrically convex function.
- {(α,m)-C} (α,m) convex function
- {(α,m)-GC} (α,m) geometrically convex function.
- {GAC} Geometric arithmetically convex function.
- {(m,h1,h2)-C} (m, h1,h2) convex function.
- {(m,h1,h2)-GAC} (m, h1,h2) geometric arithmetically convex function.
- {η-C} η convex function.
- {η-GAC} Generalized geometric arithmetically convex function with respect to η.
- {qC} Quasi-convex function.
- {CC} C- convex function.
- {cqC} C- quasi-convex function.
- {qCC} Quasi-convex function with respect to C.
- {η qC} η-quasi-convex function.

For a convex function f , the following inequality

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(u) du \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} \quad (1)$$

is known in the literature as a Hermite-Hadamard integral inequality, so known in honor of the French mathematicians who published it, independently of each other ([11,12]).

This inequality has attracted the attention of researchers in recent decades and an increase in the number of publications referring to it has been appreciated. This development has occurred in four fundamental directions:

- I) With new notions of convexity.
- II) Using different integral operators.
- III) Defining functionals, which allow obtaining new estimates of $f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx$ or $\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx - \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2}$.

IV) Using a more refined mesh, that is, instead of considering a and b , take other nodes in the interval.

In this paper we will take a tour of one of the most dynamic areas of current Mathematics (addresses I) and II) above) and we will show various work

directions, perfectly defined and some open problems.

2. THE TOUR

I) New notions of convexity.

In [3] we present the following definitions:

Definiton 1. Let $h: [0,1] \rightarrow R$ be a nonnegative function, $h \neq 0$ and $f: I = [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$. If inequality

$$f(\sigma a + m(1 - \sigma)b) \leq h^s(\sigma)f(a) + m(1 - h^s(\sigma))f(b)$$

is fulfilled for all $a,b \in I$ and $\sigma \in [0,1]$, where $m \in [0,1]$, $s \in (0,1]$. Then is said function f is a (h,m) -convex modified of first type on I .

Definiton 2. Let $h: [0,1] \rightarrow R$ be a nonnegative function, $h \neq 0$ and $f: I = [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$. If inequality

$$f(\sigma a + m(1 - \sigma)b) \leq h^s(\sigma)f(a) + m(1 - (\sigma))^s f(b)$$

is fulfilled for all $a,b \in I$ and $\sigma \in [0,1]$, where $m \in [0,1]$, $s \in (0,1]$. Then is said function f is a (h,m) -convex modified of second type on I .

Considering the triple $(h(z),m,s)$, we have the following particular cases of our definitions:

- $(z,1,1)$, then f is a convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- $(z,m,1)$, then f is a m -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- $(z,1,s)$ and $s \in (0,1]$, then f is a s -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- $(z,1,s)$ and $s \in [-1,1]$, then f is a extended s -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- (z,m,s) and $s \in (0,1]$, then f is a (s,m) -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- $(z,\alpha,1,s)$ with $\alpha \in (0,1]$, then f is a (α,s) -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- $(z,\alpha,m,1)$ with $\alpha \in (0,1]$, then f is a (α,m) -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- (z,α,m,s) with $\alpha \in (0,1]$, then f is a s - (α,m) -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.
- $(h(z),m,1)$, then we have a variant of the (h,m) -convex function on $[0,+\infty)$.

That is, our definition contains as particular cases, many of the notions of convexity reported in the literature. It is clear then, that studying the inequality

(1) under the notion of modified (h,m) -convex functions, allows us to obtain more general results than those known.

II) Different integral operators.

In different papers, we have used various operators that are generalizations of the classical Riemann Integral, of the Riemann–Liouville Fractional Integral and others. To cite just one, consider the following weighted operator:

Definition 3. Let $f \in L1(a,b)$ and let $w: [0,+\infty) \rightarrow [0,+\infty)$ be a continuous function with first order derivatives integrables on $[0,+\infty)$. Then the weighted fractional integrals are defined by (right and left, respectively):

$$J_{a+}^w \psi(\xi) = \int_a^\xi w' \left(\frac{\xi-\tau}{b-a} \right) \psi(\tau) d\tau, \quad \xi > a,$$

$$J_{b-}^w \psi(\xi) = \int_\xi^b w' \left(\frac{\tau-\xi}{b-a} \right) \psi(\tau) d\tau, \quad \xi < b.$$

Obviously if $w'(t)=1$, we obtain the Riemann Integral, while if $w'(t) = t^{\alpha-1}$ we obtain the Riemann–Liouville Fractional Integral.

In this way, we can generalize results reported for different integral operators.

Interested readers may consult [1–10], [13–20] and [22–25], for varied results.

3. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a group of results that illustrate one of the most dynamic directions in Mathematical Sciences today: the Hermite–Hadamard Inequality for convex functions. Obviously, this is not exhaustive, for example, new results for the Katugampola Fractional Integral can be obtained using these notions of convexity or some new ones.

On the other hand, obtaining new refinements for inequality (1) in the class of (h,m) -convex functions of the first type is an open problem.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kashuri, M. A. Ali, J. E. Nápoles, and Z. Zhang, "Fractional non conformable Hermite–Hadamard inequalities for generalized φ -convex functions", *Fasciculi Mathematici*, Nr 64 2020, 5–16 DOI: 10.21008/j.0044-4413.2020.0007.
- [2] B. Bayraktar, S. Butt, Sh. Shaokat, and J. E. Nápoles Valdés, *Vestnik Udmurtskogo Universiteta. Matematika. Mekhanika, Komp'yuternye Nauki*, "New Hadamard-type inequalities via $(s,m1,m2)$ -convex functions", vol. 31, issue 4, 2021, pp. 597–612.
- [3] B. Bahtiyar, and J. E. Nápoles V., "New integral inequalities of Hermite–Hadamard type in a generalized context", submitted.
- [4] B. Bayraktar, and J. E. Nápoles Valdes, *Izvestiya Instituta Matematiki i Informatiki Udmurtskogo Gosudarstvennogo Universiteta*, 2022 "NEW GENERALIZED INTEGRAL INEQUALITIES VIA (H,M) -CONVEX MODIFIED FUNCTIONS", Volume 60. Pp. 3–15
- [5] Bahtiyar Bayraktar and Juan E. Nápoles Valdés, "Integral inequalities for mappings whose derivatives are (h,m,s) -convex modified of second type via Katugampola integrals", *Annals of the University of Craiova, Mathematics and Computer Science Series*, Volume 49(2), 2022, Pages 371–383, DOI: 10.52846/ami.v49i2.1596
- [6] B. Bayraktar, J. E. Nápoles V. and F. Rabossi, "ON GENERALIZATIONS OF INTEGRAL INEQUALITIES", *Probl. Anal. Issues Anal.* Vol. 11 (29), No 2, 2022, pp. 3–23 DOI: 10.15393/j3.art.2022.11190
- [7] S. Bermudo, P. Kórus, and Juan E. Nápoles, "On q -Hermite–Hadamard inequalities for general convex functions", *Acta Math. Hungar.* 162, 2020, 364–374.
- [8] M. Bohner, A. Kashuri, P. O. Mohammed, and J. E. Nápoles V., "Hermite–Hadamard-type Inequalities for Integrals arising in Conformable Fractional Calculus", *Hacet. J. Math. Stat.* Volume 51 (3), 2022, 775–786 DOI:10.15672/hujms.946069
- [9] J. D. Galeano Delgado, J. Lloreda, J. E. Nápoles V., E. Pérez Reyes, "CERTAIN INTEGRAL INEQUALITIES OF HERMITE–HADAMARD TYPE FOR H -CONVEX FUNCTIONS", *Journal of Mathematical Control Science and Applications* Vol. 7 No. 2 (July–December), 2021, 129–140
- [10] J. D. Galeano, J. E. Nápoles, and E. Pérez, "On a general formulation of the fractional operator Riemann–Liouville and related inequalities", submitted.
- [11] J. Hadamard, "Étude sur les propriétés des fonctions entières et en particulier d'une fonction considérée par Riemann", *J. Math. Pures App.* 9, 1893, 171–216.
- [12] C. Hermite, *Sur deux limites d'une intégrale définie*, *Mathesis* 3, 82 (1883).
- [13] Artion Kashuri, Juan E. Nápoles Valdés, Muhammad Aamir Ali, and Ghulam Muhayy Ud Din, "New Integral Inequalities Using Quasi-

- Convex Functions Via Generalized Integral Operators And Their Applications”, Applied Mathematics E-Notes, 22, 2022, 221-231
- [14] P. Kórus, and J. E. Nápoles Valdés, “On some integral inequalities for (h,m) -convex functions in a generalized framework”, Carpathian Journal of Mathematics, to appear.
- [15] S. Mehmood, J. E. Nápoles Valdés, N. Fatima, and W. Aslam, “Some integral inequalities via fractional derivatives”, Adv. Studies: Euro-Tbilisi Math. J. 15(3): 2022, 31-44 (September). DOI: 10.32513/asetmj/19322008222
- [16] Juan E. Nápoles Valdés, “On the Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities involving generalized integrals”, Contrib. Math. 5, 2022, 45-51 DOI: 10.47443/cm.2022.020
- [17] J. E. Nápoles Valdés, and Bahtiyar Bayraktar, “On The Generalized Inequalities Of The Hermite-Hadamard Type”, Filomat 35:14, 2021, 4917-4924 <https://doi.org/10.2298/FIL2114917N>
- [18] J. E. Nápoles Valdés, Bahtiyar Bayraktar, and Saad Ihsan Butt, “New integral inequalities of Hermite-Hadamard type in a generalized context”, Punjab University Journal of Mathematics 53(11), 2021, 765-777 <https://doi.org/10.52280/pujm.2021.531101>
- [19] Juan E. Nápoles Valdés, Florencia Rabossi, “Generalized fractional operators and inequalities integrals”, in Bipan Hazarika, Santanu Acharjee, H. M. Srivastava (eds.), “Advances in Mathematical Analysis and its Applications”, Chapman and Hall/CRC, New York, 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003330868>
- [20] J. E. Nápoles Valdés, Florencia Rabossi, and Hijaz Ahmad, “INEQUALITIES OF THE HERMITE-HADAMARD TYPE, FOR FUNCTIONS (H,M) -CONVEX MODIFIED OF THE SECOND TYPE”, Commun. Combin., Cryptogr. & Computer Sci., 1, 2021, 33-43
- [21] J. E. Nápoles Valdes, F. Rabossi, and A. D. Samaniego, “CONVEX FUNCTIONS: ARIADNE’S THREAD OR CHARLOTTE’S SPIDERWEB?”, Advanced Mathematical Models & Applications Vol.5, No.2, 2020, pp.176-191
- [22] J. E. Nápoles Valdes, J. M. Rodríguez, and J. M. Sigarreta, “New Hermite-Hadamard Type Inequalities Involving Non-Conformable Integral Operators”, Symmetry 11, 2019, 1108; doi:10.3390/sym11091108
- [23] M. Vivas-Cortez, S. Kermausuor, and J. E. Nápoles Valdés, “Hermite-Hadamard Type Inequalities for Coordinated Quasi-Convex Functions via Generalized Fractional Integrals”, in P. Debnath et al. (eds.), “Fixed Point Theory and Fractional Calculus: Recent Advances and Applications”..., Forum for Interdisciplinary Mathematics... 2022, Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-0668-8_16
- [24] M. Vivas-Cortez, P. Kórus, and Juan E. Nápoles Valdés, “Some generalized Hermite-Hadamard-Fejér inequality for convex functions”, Advances in Difference Equations 2021:199 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13662-021-03351-7>
- [25] M. Vivas-Cortez, Juan E. Nápoles Valdés, and J. A. Guerrero, “Som Hermite-Hadamard Weighted Integral Inequalities for (hm) -Convex Modified Functions”, Appl. Math. Inf. Sc 16 No.1, 2022, 25-33 <http://dx.doi.org/10.18576/amis/160103>